

Study of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II), Copper(II), Palladium(II) and Platinum(II) with Pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and Acetylacetonone

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Mixed ligand complexes of the types [MLL'], [MLL'A] and [MLE.H₂O] have been prepared, where M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, or Pt^{II}, L = pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde, L' = acetylacetonone, A = ammonia or alkylamine, and E = ethanalamine. These complexes have been characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic, conductance and spectral studies.

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on mixed ligand complexes, we report slightly different types of mixed ligand complexes in the present communication.

Experimental

[MLL'] type of complexes, where M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}, L = pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde, and L' = acetylacetonone, were prepared by adding pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde (Fluka) and acetylacetonone to the metal acetate solution in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio. The coloured solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. On reaction with excess of ammonia or alkylamines these gave [MLL'A] type complexes (A = ammonia or alkylamine) which on refluxing with ethanalamine on a water bath for 2-3 h gave [MLE.H₂O] type complexes (E = ethanalamine). These complexes were recrystallised from methanol.

Results and Discussion

All the mixed ligand complexes give satisfactory C, H, N and metal analysis. [MLE.H₂O] type complexes indicated the presence of a water molecule. Very small molar conductance values (3.2-7.2 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) suggest these complexes to be non-electrolytic in nature.

The Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes are found diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic (μ_{eff} , 1.88 B.M.) at room temperature.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed ligand Ni^{II} complexes in methanol gave two bands at 610-620 and 535-550 nm assignable to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{8g}, respectively. The Cu^{II} complex gave one band at 635-645 nm assignable to the transition ²B_{1g} → ²E_g. The Pd^{II}

complexes exhibited three bands in the narrow ranges at 440-450, 375-380 and 315-320 nm assigned to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}, respectively. The Pt^{II} complexes also gave three bands at 310-320, 350-355 and 420-430 nm assignable to the transitions ¹A₁ → ¹B₁, ¹A₁ → ¹A₂ and ¹A₁ → ³A₂, respectively. These data indicate a square-planar structure²⁻⁶ for the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes.

In the ir spectra of complexes [MLL'] and [MLL'A], no band was observed at 3300-3100 or 3600-3400 cm⁻¹, indicating that hydrogen of the NH group of pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and the OH group of acetylacetonone get dissociated on complexation. Spectra of the [MLL'] complexes show bands at 1630 cm⁻¹ (aldehydic C=O) and 1570 cm⁻¹ (C-O) of the acetylacetonone. In the ir spectra of the [MLL'A] complexes (in which R=H), the band at 1630 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new band appeared at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N imine linkage). The band at 1570 cm⁻¹ (C=O) of acetylacetonone remains unchanged indicating that it does not undergo condensation. The appearance of the band at 3300-3100 cm⁻¹ (free N-H) was absent in the mixed ligand complexes derived from alkylamines. The ir spectra of the [MLE.H₂O] type complexes showing a band at 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH stretch) confirms the presence of water molecule and the band at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The appearance of two new bands at 500-480 and 570-560 cm⁻¹ in the above type of complexes suggests the presence of M-O and M-N bondings⁶.

On the basis of the above investigations, the [MLL'], [MLL'A] and [MLE.H₂O] type complexes may be represented by the structures as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of mixed ligand complexes.
 where $M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}$ or Pt^{II}
 $R = H, CH_3$ or C_2H_5
 $E = \text{ethanolamine}$

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